

Artificial Intelligence

Issues and Perspectives

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Abstract: In today's world in order to spice up our daily communication, we often humanize what electronic devices do. And also, we electricize what human brain thinks and does. In this outline, this essay gives more information about the emergence of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the relation between the human and machines. The great debate is whether human dominates machines our machine dominates human. In a way, the present world depends on machines for everything, even our daily routine is systematized in this way. For example, our day begins with an alarm and ends with a goodnight message from our loved one. So, but for this reason we cannot come to a conclusion that humans are dominated by machine rather man has the ability and capacity to control everything. Because man is the creator and programmer of this feelingless devices, so it is systematized by man. But now in the present situation it varies downward. Machines take over everything. In this essay mainly focuses on the problems of humanizing machines and gives some philosophical answer to this quest. In present scenario factories, institutions depend more on machines, in the way human work is not concerned and they suffer for the daily wage. Jobless, fear, anxiety, suicide become the cause of it. For this, psychologically manpower has to be prioritized and man should know how to handle and generate and program the system apart from switching on and off. This man will be supreme being who has feelings, creative mind and ability to bring forth the society. In the conclusion, it clearly says that only man or only machine cannot survive for the growth of the society but both should have a balanced way, in which the society grows upward and the human power is being valued.

1. INTRODUCTION

Artificial Intelligence was born in 1956 as the off-spring of the newly-created paradigm of cognition. As such, it inherited a strong philosophical legacy of functionalism. Dualism, and positivism. Artificial intelligence (AI) is a set of technologies that enable computers to perform a variety of advanced functions, including the ability to see, understand and translate spoken and written language, analyze data, make recommendations, and more.

Artificial Intelligence is another way is to make computational models of human thought processes. This is a stronger and more constrained view of what the enterprise is. It is not enough to make a program that seems to behave the way humans do you. A lot of people have worked on this in cognitive science and in an area called cognitive neuroscience. The research strategy is to affiliate with someone who does experiments that reveal something about what goes on inside people's heads and then build computational models that mirror those kinds of processes." A crucial question is to decide at what level to mirror what goes on inside people's heads." (John Haugeland, 1985, 47-48). Someone might try to model it a very high-level, for example, dividing processing into high- level vision, memory, and cognition modules; they try to get the modularity to be accurate but they do not worry too much about the details of how the modules are implemented. Other people might pick the neuron as a kind of computational unit that feels like it's justified in terms of neurophysiology, and then take that abstract neuron and make computational mechanisms out of it. It seems justified because we know that brains are made out of neurons. So, it's hard to know how to match up what we know about brains with computational models.

2. Definition: Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science that emphasizes the creation of intelligent machines that work and reacts like humans. Some of the activities computers with artificial intelligence are designed for include: Speech recognition, Learning, Planning, Problem-solving. "Artificial intelligence is a branch of computer science that aims to create intelligent machines." (Simon

and Newell, 1975, 35-37). It has become an essential part of the technology industry. The research associated with artificial intelligence is highly technical and specialized.

The core problems of artificial intelligence include programming computers for certain traits such as:

- Knowledge
- Reasoning
- Problem solving
- Perception
- Learning
- Planning
- Ability to manipulate and move objects

Knowledge engineering is a core part of artificial intelligence research. Machines can often act and react like humans only if they have abundant information relating to the world. Artificial intelligence must have access to objects, categories, properties and relations between all of them to implement knowledge engineering. Initiating common sense, reasoning and problem-solving power in machines is a difficult and tedious approach.

Machine-learning is another core part of artificial intelligence. Learning without any kind of supervision requires an ability to identify patterns in streams of inputs, whereas learning with adequate supervision involves classification and numerical regressions. Classification determines the category an object belongs to and regression deals with obtaining a set of numerical input or output examples, thereby discovering functions enabling the generation of suitable outputs from respective inputs. Mathematical analysis of machine learning algorithms and their performance is a well-defined branch of theoretical computer science often referred to as computational learning theory. Machine perception deals with the capability to use sensory inputs to deduce the different aspects of the world, while computer vision is the power to analyze visual inputs with a few sub-problems such as facial, object and gesture recognition. Robotics is also a major field related to AI. Robots require intelligence to handle tasks such as object manipulation and navigation, along with sub-problems of localization, motion planning and mapping.

3. Merits and Demerits of Artificial intelligence

- Advantages of artificial intelligence
 - a. It defines a more powerful and more useful computers
 - b. It introduces a new and improved interface for human interaction.
 - c. It introduces a new technique to solve new problems.
 - d. It handles the information better than humans.
 - e. It is very helpful for the conversion of information into knowledge.
 - f. It improves work efficiency so reduce the duration of time to accomplish a task in comparison to humans.
- Disadvantages of artificial intelligence
 - a. The implementation cost of AI is very high.
 - b. The difficulties with software development for AI implementation are that the development of software is slow and expensive. Few efficient programmers are available to develop software to implement artificial intelligence.
 - c. A robot is one of the implementations of Artificial intelligence with them replacing jobs and lead to serve unemployment.
 - d. Machines can easily lead to destruction if the implementation of machine put in the wrong hands the results are hazardous for human beings.

4. Features of Artificial Intelligence

The Artificial Intelligence has the tremendous power to change the things, here are four ways artificial intelligence will change everything:

4.1 Internet of Things

Have you noticed how computers have gotten smaller while getting smarter? They've also gotten cheaper: now there's a computer inside anything with an on/off switch. All of these newly intelligent devices toasters to toothbrushes, thermostats and light bulbs and cars are now being networked, talking to each other, and businesses, and consumers (Haugeland,1981, 7-8). Why shouldn't your car tell your house that you're nearly home so that the house can tell the oven to

preheat to the proper temperature for that fish it knows you just bought, because you made the purchase with your phone and your phone told it so? So, behind every device are a customer, and the next generation of customers expect a connected, smart experience. We're talking about a lot of connected things: six billion of them that, says Gartner, will be requesting support by 2018. Those billions of connected things mean huge volumes of customer data. Businesses need to be smart about the way they gather, digest, and apply that data, which is the life blood of lot... if it can be properly used.

4.2 Data and Analytics

A huge gap is growing between companies and customers. For all the data customers are creating, less than 1% is analyzed, such that 77% of customers say they are not engaged with businesses. "There are so many ways to read data and so many conclusions to be drawn about customer behaviour and preferences yet most of this potential insight is falling by the wayside because businesses aren't prioritizing the analysis of that data" (Granlund,1999, 101-126). New tools reveal useful insights about the customer. These insights exist along a spectrum of Intelligence; the most basic tools require you to "pull" information out of them, while the most intelligent tools "push" information to you, anticipating what you're going to want to know. For the latter, we turn to machine learning.

4.3 Machine Learning

With machine learning, computer systems can take all this customer data and build on it, operating not just on what's been programmed but also adapting to changes. Algorithms adapt to data, developing behaviours not programmed in advance. Learning to read and recognize context means a digital assistant could scan emails and extract what it knows you'll want to know. Inherent in this learning is the ability to make predictions about future behaviour, to know the customer more intimately and not just be responsive, but proactive.

4.4 Prediction

Big data and analysis produce patterns, and when smarter machines are able to read patterns and learn from them, they can figure out what might come next, make deductions that are better than just assumptions, and make

conclusions that are better than just guesses. The promise of a “digital assistant” (Winograd, 1986, 43-44) is not the robot voice that answers our questions about temperature and movie times, but that knows our patterns, learns from them, and reminds us to leave now in order to beat our record of arriving 2 minutes late 80% of the time.

The system needs to be fed, and from that comes smarter machines, connected devices, and the ability to predict our needs and wants. The more quality information we can give to the system, the smarter it will get (Winograd, 1986, 70).

5. Humanizing machines

In the present age, Machine Learning is on the verge of transforming our lives. The need to provide intelligent machines with a moral compass is of great importance, especially at a time when humanity is more divided than ever. Machine Learning has endless possibilities, but if used improperly, it could have far-reaching and lasting negative effects. These new technologies may one day eliminate the requirement for state-guided monopolies of force and potentially create a fairer society. Machine Learning could signal a new revolution for humanity; one with heart and soul. If we can take full advantage of the power of technology to augment our ability to make good, moral decisions and comprehend the complex chain of effects on society and the world at large, then the potential benefits of prosocial technologies could be substantial (Presbury, 2007, 55).

6 Man: Superior to machines

Human brain can work constantly and more efficiently to create and make use of something wisely. Humans are capable of learning, grasping, understanding the concept of various things. Humans are curious to discover and create new things. Humans are multi-talented whereas machines are not. Artificial intelligence is also created by human brains and their functions are limited.

Machines are superior to humans in terms of speed and accuracy. Calculators for example work more accurately and speedily than human brains to make calculations. Human brain programs the functioning of any kind of machine. Human brains develop naturally

by observing, experimenting, learning and discovering, but the improvement in machinery is possible only when its mechanical brain is fed by humans. Also, there is no emotional intelligence in machines. Emotions play a major role in developing human brain. Thus, the capacity of machines is limited whereas humans are always experimenting, creating, inventing and discovering more and more.

7. Machine dominates human

An AI takeover is a hypothetical scenario in which an artificial intelligence (AI) becomes the dominant form of intelligence on Earth, as computer programs or robots effectively take the control of the planet away from the human species. Possible scenarios include replacement of the entire human workforce, takeover by a super intelligent AI, and the popular notion of a robot uprising. Some public figures, such as Stephen Hawking and Elon Musk, have advocated research into precautionary measures to ensure future super intelligent machines remain under human control (Bostrom, 2019, 112). There are many kinds in Artificial intelligence AI and here are the some of its features.

7.1 Human agency

Individuals are experiencing a loss of control over their lives. Decision-making on key aspects of digital life is automatically ceded to code-driven, “black box” tools. People lack input and do not learn the context about how the tools work. They sacrifice independence, privacy and power over choice; they have no control over these processes. This effect will deepen as automated systems become more prevalent and complex.

7.2 Data abuse

Data use and surveillance in complex systems is designed for profit or for exercising power. Most AI tools are and will be in the hands of companies striving for profits or governments striving for power. Values and ethics are often not baked into the digital systems making people’s decisions for them. These systems are globally networked and not easy to regulate or rein in.

7.3 Job loss

The AI takeover of jobs will widen economic divides, leading to social upheaval. The efficiencies and other economic advantages of code-based machine intelligence will continue to disrupt all aspects of human work.

While some expect new jobs will emerge, others worry about massive job losses, widening economic divides and social upheavals, including populist uprisings.

7.4 Dependence lock-in

Reduction of individuals' cognitive, social and survival skills. Many see AI as augmenting human capacities but some predict the opposite – that people's deepening dependence on machine-driven networks will erode their abilities to think for themselves, take action independent of automated systems and interact effectively with others.

8. Philosophical solutions

Global gave give many kinds of examples how the man becomes superior to the artificial intelligence. And in other man can dominate the Machine rather machines dominate human. Here I put forward some of the value system which is connected philosophically, how man controls machines and how it becomes better for the development of human and for the society.

8.1 Good is No. 1

Improve human collaboration across borders and Stakeholder groups. Digital cooperation to serve humanity's best interests is the top priority. Ways must be found for people around the world to come to common understandings and agreements - to join forces to facilitate the innovation of widely accepted approaches aimed at tackling wicked problems and maintaining control over complex human-digital networks.

8.2 Values-based system

Develop policies to assure AI will be directed at 'humanness' and common good. Adopt a 'moonshot mentality' to build inclusive, decentralized intelligent digital networks 'imbued with empathy' that help humans aggressively ensure that technology meets social and ethical responsibilities. Some new level of regulatory and certification process will be necessary.

8.3 Prioritize people

Alter economic and political systems to better help humans ‘race with the robots. Reorganize economic and political systems toward the goal of expanding humans’ capacities and capabilities in order to heighten human/AI collaboration and staunch trends that would compromise human relevance in the face of programmed intelligence.

9. Locke’s theory of knowledge and artificial intelligence

Lockean theory of knowledge is classified as sensitive, demonstrative and intuitive typologies of knowledge bear strong similarities and differences with the working of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence operates intuitively, demonstratively and sensitively by a specific mode of sense-representation. Thus, the study infers the position of Lockean theory of knowledge and the artificial intelligence; it would appear that Locke has not been dealt justice over the years. Upon a closer look, his system of knowledge appears truly robust even today. The charge that his system leads to solipsism appears to be founded on a failure of his detractors to recognize that Locke himself advocated a different criterion for judging the certainty of knowledge derived from sensory experience (Axtell, James, 1968, 143), While Locke granted the highest degree of certainty and evidence to intuitive and demonstrative knowledge, he certainly did not exclude knowledge derived from sensory experience, which charges solipsism advocate. Locke suggested that knowledge derived from such experience could not extend to general truths; this suggests that any such general beliefs or faith which was derived from experience could not attain the same degree of certainty as that obtainable with intuitive and demonstrative knowledge. Locke implied, in his discussion of analogy and probability, and his discussions of the origin of error, that we should continually seek to improve the degree of certainty of any such general truths derived from sensitive knowledge. A careful reading of Locke suggests that he would not have a strictly univocal use for the terms: truth, knowledge and certainty. The artificial intelligence and the Lockean theory of knowledge can have the certain degree of influence with each other to prove the knowledge.

10. Conclusion

It is nothing good or bad to artificial intelligence (AI) it will simply respond with results that are derived completely by its learning. The good or badness of AI will depend on how well we train the AI, and perhaps most importantly how well we test the artificial intelligence.

We want humans to behave more and more like machines and on the other hand, we want machines to behave more and more like humans. In that way machines are not Superior to man but the man who is the creator of this machines are superior. But the man has to be systematized in the way of using the artificial intelligence.

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Article Received Jan 30, 2023; Accepted 11 Feb 2023; Words: 3108

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